

Programming Language Extension Using Structured Query Language for Database Access

Chapman Eze Nnadozie

Abstract—Relational databases constitute a very vital tool for the effective management and administration of both personal and organizational data. Data access ranges from a single user database management software to a more complex distributed server system. This paper intends to appraise the use a programming language extension like structured query language (SQL) to establish links to a relational database (Microsoft Access 2013) using Visual C++ 9 programming language environment. The methodology used involves the creation of tables to form a database using Microsoft Access 2013, which is Object Linking and Embedding (OLE) database compliant. The SQL command is used to query the tables in the database for easy extraction of expected records inside the visual C++ environment. The findings of this paper reveal that records can easily be accessed and manipulated to filter exactly what the user wants, such as retrieval of records with specified criteria, updating of records, and deletion of part or the whole records in a table.

Keywords—Data access, database, database management system, OLE, programming language, records, relational database, software, SQL, table.

I. INTRODUCTION

EVERY institution all over the world makes use of one or more databases that is created using Database Management System (DBMS) software to meet individual or institutional needs. Software such as Microsoft Excel, Microsoft Access, and Microsoft Visual FoxPro are used to create a single user application, while software such as Oracle and SQL Server are used if the user is building applications that need to access large, shared databases. All DBMS software supports the use of SQL as a common standard for manipulation of data from database tables [1].

This paper will be focusing on the use of SQL to maintain, manipulate and access databases from Visual C++ via OLE to meet specific needs. OLE, just like Open Database Connectivity (ODBC), is an Application Programming Interface (API) that is capable of linking any database application that is OLE-compliant to its appropriate DBMS software through its driver. OLE is implemented as a standard SQL-based interface which is a vital part of the Windows Operating System.

II. OBJECTIVES

This study intends:-

- To find out a common interface through which any database can be accessed.

Chapman Eze Nnadozie is with the Department of Computer Science, Abubakar Tatari Ali Polytechnic, Bauchi, Nigeria (e-mail: chapsuccess@gmail.com).

- To find out how a database connection can be established in Visual C++ programming language environment.
- To determine a standard programming language extension with which queries can be issued in order to access and manipulate database tables from Visual C++.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A database can be seen as an integrated collection of logically related records or objects. Databases, consisting of tables that contain fields of data, are necessary in every organization for its effective management. Therefore, business applications need to maintain, manipulate, and access records stored in database tables. Each field in a database contains specific data, while a collection of related fields make up a record. DBMS software is used to maintain a database [2].

The older versions of windows operating system has the ODBC interface implemented as a standard SQL-based interface with the ability of handling any form of databases [3]. ODBC API architecture is such that its manager has the driver for all DBMS software. This architecture enables the DBMS vendors to focus on the creation of specific driver for their respective software without worrying about the entire path to an application [4]. Newer computers with latter versions of windows operating system like Windows 7, Windows 8 and Windows 10 are using OLE to connect to OLE databases.

Fig. 1 shows that an ODBC application makes database calls to the ODBC Driver Manager which in turn translates it to the appropriate database driver to establish a database connection. In other words, what the ODBC manager does is to link you to the appropriate driver for the data source you want through which your database can be accessed for maintenance, editing and querying as the case may require using SQL statements [2].

SQL is a standard relational database language for accessing and manipulating databases. This implies that SQL statements are used to query database tables to extract or change the information contained therein. With SQL commands, data can easily be extracted from any type of DBMS. The following are the basic types of SQL statements: SELECT, INSERT, DELETE and UPDATE [5].

- 1) **SELECT:** This is the simplest form of query that selects rows and columns from one or more tables in a database. The basic form of a select statement is:

```
SELECT {DISTINCT} /Select – list/  
FROM table_list  
{WHERE condition }  
{ORDER BY field_list {DESC } }
```


Fig. 1 ODBC architecture [2]

THE WHERE CLAUSE

This is used to retrieve records that satisfy certain conditions. The WHERE clause condition can contain operators <, >, =, <=, >=, <>, and Like. The Like operator is used for pattern matching with wildcard characters – percent (%) and underscore (_).

ORDER CLAUSE

This clause is used to sort the rows in a table. The named column becomes the basis for the sorting of the table either in ascending or descending order.

2) **INSERT:** This is used to add data into a table. The basic format is:

```

INSERT INTO table_name
      (column_lists)
VALUES (value_lists).
    
```

Table_name refers to the name of the table. Column_lists refer to the names of the columns you wish to add a new record to in your table. Value_lists refer to the corresponding values you wish to insert into the table. Any column that is not specified is given a null value. However, column_lists is omitted if you are adding values to all the columns in a table. Insert Into and Values are key words.

3) **DELETE:** This statement is used to remove an existing record in a table that meets the WHERE condition. It can also be used to delete an entire table from a database. Its format is:

```

DELETE FROM table_name
OR
DELETE FROM table_name
WHERE search_condition.
    
```

The table_name is the name of the table in which you can delete rows. The search_condition in the WHERE clause is the same as in the SELECT command.

4) **UPDATE:** This statement enables you to change a group of records in a table. It works directly on the source database table to update the data. Its format is as follows:

```

UPDATE table_name
SET      columnname1=value1,
columnname2=value2,...,
columnnameN=valueN
    
```

WHERE condition.

Table_name refers to the table to be updated. SET is a keyword. Columnname refers to the specific column you wish to replace its value with a new value. The where clause provides the condition that determines which rows to update.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The researcher creates a database (StudResults) using the DBMS software Microsoft Access 2013. This database contains three relational database tables namely – DOT114 (with attributes AdmNo, LName, FName, ContAss, Exam, Total, and Grade), DOTSR (with attributes AdmNo, Dot111, Dot112, Dot113, Dot114, Dot115, Gns101, Gns111, and Gns121), and DOTGP (with attributes AdmNo, Tcur, Tcuc, Csp, Cgpa, and Remarks). 'AdmNo' is the unique key for this relational database, and a one-to-one relationship exists between the tables. This database (StudResults) is then connected to within the Visual C++ programming language environment.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation is done in the visual C++ environment, and it entails the querying of the relational database earlier created using Microsoft access 2013 software to filter desired records. The programming language extension is to be used on the database is SQL which provides a standard means of maintaining, manipulating and accessing database tables. Using SQL, the researcher will be able to perform at least the following basic operations:

- Retrieval of records from database tables.
- Insertion of new record(s) into a database table.
- Updating of records in database tables.
- Deleting of an existing record in a table.
- Deleting of an entire table that is no longer needed.

VI. INPUT AND OUTPUT

Below are some screen shots of the inputs and their respective corresponding outputs in visual C++ 9 environment.

Fig. 2 Sample from a SELECT command

Fig. 3 Sample from another SELECT command

Fig. 4 Sample from an INSERT command

Fig. 5 Sample from an UPDATE command

Fig. 6 Sample from another UPDATE command

Fig. 7 Sample from a DELETE command

VII. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Typically, a DBMS is designed to create and manage a database. A database, which is a collection of related records, is composed of several fields called data members in C++ [6]. ODBC API, which is now being replaced by OLE API, has a standard SQL-based interface to work with any type of database thereby making database access a renowned reality. This is because you can create a database using any DBMS software, and administer it from a programming language such as Visual C++ to extract records from the database. Having established a connection to the database, the basic SQL commands can be used to query the database tables to obtain the desired results.

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